

TRANSFORMING HEALTHCARE:

Case Studies for
Ireland's Sláintecare
Implementation

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Shauna Rust is a Mitchell scholar who is studying at University College Dublin to complete a Masters in Public Policy.

Shauna has developed a deep interest in health policy and reform. She has studied and published extensively on these issues in America.

As part of her studies in Ireland she was invited to work in my office in Dail Eireann to look at the Slaintecare report published in May 2017, the subsequent Slaintecare Implementation Strategy published August 2018 and Slaintecare Action Plan published March 2019. Additionally Shauna has observed the activity of the Joint Oireachtas Health Committee as it examines health policy and interacts with the day to day problems which impact on our health service.

Shauna has researched health reform programmes in USA, UK (Scotland) and New Zealand to establish what can be learnt from their experiences of health reform which would add to the Slaintecare reform initiatives as they are developed and implemented.

Shauna's paper is a comprehensive analysis of health reform which is developing in Ireland. Her analysis is a valuable addition to the process of change which is essential in the Irish health services as it moves to new models of care, integration and digitalisation of health records and information gathering. These are essential components for improving patient outcomes and efficient spending of scarce resources.

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1) United States VA system – Leadership & Evidence

The United States Veterans Health Administration, known simply as the VA, is the country's largest integrated health care system, providing care to over 9 million veterans enrolled (U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs). The VA provides care for military veterans with service-related disabilities, as well as lower-income veterans and their families (Stires, 2006). By the early 1990s, the VA had developed a reputation for delivering poor-quality care and failing to meet the health needs of veterans returning from military service. However, in 1995, newly-appointed VA leader Kenneth Kizer led an aggressive campaign to reform the VA through his "Vision for Change." The result was a fully integrated health system with a strong reliance on regional networks, primary care, health technology, and patient safety (Skydell, 1998). The following case study examines how Kizer's leadership of the VA transformed healthcare delivery at the system level to improve quality of care while also containing costs, and lessons learned for Irish Sláintecare reform.

Parallels in Health System Issues: VA and the Irish system

A. Public Mistrust

Prior to the 1995 reforms, there was a profound lack of public trust in the VA health system. The VA was characterized as a "centralised, punitive, and bureaucratic" system (Payne, 2012), offering low-quality care in substandard facilities (Stires, 2006). Reports from the U.S. government watchdog (Government Accountability Office), news media, and peer-reviewed articles all revealed glaring issues with the VA's quality of care, fragmented care, overutilization of hospital services, and poor customer service (Government Accountability Office, 1987, 1994; Smith et al., 1996). Veterans also experienced difficulties with accessing the care they needed, sometimes waiting months for appointments or having to travel hundreds of miles to see a provider (Government Accountability Office, 1993). The media often reported on the VA system's failures and running the VA was widely seen as a "career ender" (Payne, 2012). Similarly, the Irish HSE, the Republic's largest employer, often faces criticism for being too bureaucratic and particularly failing public patients.

B. Hospital-centric System

Additionally, the pre-reform VA underutilized primary and preventive care, and instead had a strong reliance on hospital care. Strikingly, only 10 percent of veterans had a primary care physician (akin to a general practitioner, GP, in the Irish context). Patients were seeing different specialists (consultants, in the Irish context) for each chronic condition and were not receiving necessary preventive care (e.g. vaccinations) (Stires, 2006). This is similar to the outlook in today's Irish health system, where only certain patients are provided free GP visits, and the out-of-pocket cost for a GP visit deters many from seeking primary care. This creates increased reliance on hospitals for emergency or acute care when chronic conditions have not been properly managed in the primary care or community setting.

VA Innovations

A. Health Technology

One of the hallmarks of the 1995 VA reforms was the introduction of a system-wide electronic health record (EHR) system. The VistA (Veterans Health Information and Technology Architecture) system was rolled out across 172 hospitals in three years (Payne, 2012). While previously paper records were the standard practice throughout most of the system, the VistA EHR system allows providers to track patients' health across care settings and across geographical boundaries. Not only does the EHR provide information about the patient across the life course, it also can reduce medical errors, provide clinical guidance, and assist with health system performance measurement. Drawbacks to the implementation of a system-wide EHR include the high start-up costs and the potential lost time for providers when inputting patient data into the system. However, EHR adoption is an investment in a high-quality health system with reduced errors and the potential to lower costs. And, it could be argued that physicians would spend just as much time with paperwork prior to electronic systems, and perhaps this is an opportunity to engage Irish clinicians across the scope of practice, so the burden of maintaining patient EHRs is not solely on the GP or physician (Oliver, 2007). As VA reform architect Ken Kizer puts it, "the single most important thing that can be done to improve the quality, safety, and efficiency of health care today is to widely implement electronic health records" (Stires, 2006).

Furthermore, the VA has incorporated telehealth and remote patient monitoring into its care model in order to treat patients with the aim of reducing preventable hospitalizations and reducing mortality. For example, a VA health center can monitor a patient's vital statistics remotely through a "Telebuddy" placed in the patient's home. When abnormalities are noticed by VA staff, clinicians can alter the patient's care plan

(e.g. adjusting a medication dose) or call them in for further observation and treatment if necessary (Stires, 2006). The VA estimates that the Telebuddy technology has reduced hospital bed days and ER visits by 30 percent each (Glabman, 2007). Uptake of telehealth and remote patient monitoring modalities could be especially helpful in rural Ireland, where residents might have to travel long distances to reach a health centre or hospital, and in monitoring older adults who may be home-bound and require special assistance to see a health care provider. Other key pieces of health technology reform in the VA system include a barcode medication administration system and an automated prescription filling system.

B. Regional Health Networks

Key complaints with the pre-reform VA health system were that care was fragmented, of irregular quality, sometimes difficult to access, and too reliant on inpatient hospital care. To address this multi-pronged issue, the 1995 VA reforms introduced veteran integrated service networks (VISNs), which geographically organized the VA's 1100-plus health care delivery sites into 22 VISN areas (now 23). The idea was to equitably distribute health resources and infrastructure among catchment groups of about 250,000 veterans each. A typical VISN “encompassed 7–10 VA hospitals, 25–30 ambulatory care clinics, 5–7 nursing homes, 1–2 domiciliaries³, and 10–15 counselling centres” (Kenneth W. Kizer & Dudley, 2009). The VISN model could be a helpful example in the re-structuring of Irish CHOs and Hospital Groups, which would also organize health infrastructure on a geographic basis, although the facility type mixture might differ. The VISNs are tailored to the needs of a veteran population, which may be older and have more complex conditions (including mental health) than the general population.

The introduction of VISNs also allowed for the movement towards a more primary care-based system that prioritized preventive care and less reliance on hospital-based care (Armstrong, Levesque, Perlin, Rick, & Schectman, 2005). This is very much in line with the ideals of the Sláintecare reforms, which would reorient the Irish health system “towards integrated primary and community care, consistent with the highest quality of patient safety in as short a time-frame as possible” (Committee on the Future of Healthcare, 2017). The VA reforms aimed to integrate and coordinate services across the care continuum, and introducing universal primary care was a key component. Through the VISN reorganization, VA medical centres moved from a specialist-based (i.e. consultant-based) model to adopting primary care team structures. VA medical centres implemented general/internal medicine programs, training more clinicians in primary care and internal medicine, and also assigned patients to individual primary care providers. Subsequently, primary care enrolment more than doubled, from only 38% in 1993 to 95% by 1999 (Yano, Simon, Lanto, & Rubenstein, 2007). This could be a model for transitioning care in Ireland to more outpatient, community care settings, providing universal access to GP care, and bolstering the primary care workforce.

Overall, the VISNs organized care for veterans into geographic service areas that emphasized primary care and created a more accountable health system, as outlined below by Kizer & Dudley (2009):

The VISN became the system’s basic operating unit. The idea was that it would provide a structural template for coordinating services, pooling resources, and ensuring continuity of care; reducing service duplication and administrative redundancies when appropriate; improving the consistency and predictability of services; promoting more effective and accountable management; and overall, optimizing health care value.

FIGURE 1. Veterans Integrated Service Networks (VISNs). U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs (2018).

3 institutional homes for aged and disabled veterans who cannot care for themselves

C. Cost Containment and Re-investment

While healthcare costs were significantly rising throughout the US in the 1990s, the VA managed to hold cost increases steady while providing high-quality healthcare and bringing in hundreds of thousands of new patients. Notably, the VA did not receive any specific funding source for its revamp, but rather used its annual budget appropriation and re-investment in savings to generate income for further reforms. For example, the VA was able to generate savings by “eliminating excess capacity (e.g., closing acute care beds), negotiat[ing] more favorable pricing on needed goods and services (e.g., pharmaceuticals and the National Formulary), or provid[ing] care in lower-cost settings (e.g., moving more care to the outpatient setting when clinically appropriate).” Then, the VA was allowed to re-invest any cost savings into new initiatives, such as rolling out the VistA EHR system or the introduction of more community-based outpatient clinics (Kenneth W. Kizer & Dudley, 2009).

Allowing the HSE to re-invest any cost savings into new initiatives to further the Sláintecare reforms and continue to improve health system capacity could be a crucial tool for success. Also of note, the Irish system may not be able to realize similar cost savings by closing hospital beds, as the VA system did, given that there are often waiting lists for public patients to access care.

D. Innovation, Quality Improvement, and Patient Safety

The VA reforms also illustrate the importance of creating a health system with a continuous improvement lens, where innovation, patient safety, and quality improvement are prized features throughout all levels of the system.

D1. Bottom-up Innovation

Under Kizer’s leadership, VA medical centre staff were encouraged to test out new ideas for improving care delivery and had the opportunity to present their ideas to VA leadership for potential system-wide adoption if they demonstrated promising results. For example, a nurse at a VA medical centre in Kansas piloted the use of a patient barcode system for prescription administration, and found that it reduced errors by 70% through matching patients, drugs, and doctors’ orders. A staffer mentioned the project to Kizer at a monthly meeting, and Kizer followed-up on the suggestion, visited the pilot site, and decided to roll out the barcode system to all VA hospitals by 2000 (Stires, 2006; Wideman, Whittler, & Anderson, 2005). Seeking input and innovative ideas from clinicians and health system administrators across all levels could be an effective way to engage providers and HSE staff in the Sláintecare reforms, and empower them as leaders in Irish healthcare transformation.

D2. Quality Improvement and Patient Safety

Performance was tracked across the VA system, through the assistance of the new VistA EHR system, in order to monitor clinicians’ usage of evidence-based best practices for prevention and chronic disease care. By implementing this performance management system, VA leaders could track patterns and outcomes, and tailor quality improvement initiatives to the most pressing concerns (Naditz, 2008).

Along with performance measurement, quality improvement efforts were introduced across the VA system through evidence-based clinical guidelines, collaboration with the Institute for Healthcare Improvement to reduce waiting times and improve access to care, and empowering clinicians to lead quality improvement work (e.g. VA National Quality Scholars Fellowship Program) (K. W. Kizer, Demakis, & Feussner, 2000). Similarly, the VA launched a patient safety initiative in 1997 that sought to reduce medical errors and improve health outcomes through the introduction of best practices, modifying organizational culture, research, and partnership with national patient safety organizations (Bagian et al., 2001).

Another notable reform was the creation of the VA Lessons Learned Project, a knowledge management tool for virtual learning on successes and errors happening in the health system. The Lessons Learned Project was designed for rapid-cycle quality improvement, so innovations and best practices could be quickly diffused throughout the system and clinicians could learn from errors in closer to real-time (R. Charles, 2000; Kenneth W. Kizer & Dudley, 2009).

In the Irish setting, there are a multitude of quality improvement and patient safety activities that clinicians and health care administrators could take on to improve care delivery and health outcomes. In particular, efforts could focus on creating clinical guidelines for a) preventive and primary care and/or b) treatment of certain chronic conditions, as well as the creation of safety “bundles” summarizing best practices for Irish clinicians to follow. Further, Irish health system leaders should explore opportunities to

empower clinicians and staff to take on quality improvement and patient safety as core tenets of health reform, and identify the resources needed to train clinician leaders and carry out change in the clinical setting.

Reform Outcomes

As a result of the aforementioned outcomes, along with a host of other interventions not listed, the VA health system was fundamentally transformed following Ken Kizer’s “Vision for Change” in 1995. The reforms altered how care was delivered, re-organizing the system into veteran integrated service networks (VISNs), each responsible for a specific geographic region with all levels of care from primary to tertiary. The new system emphasized primary and outpatient care, and was bolstered by a universal electronic health record (EHR) system and other health technologies.

The result was a health system that was re-characterized as providing “the best medical care in the US” and as a model for health care reform (Payne, 2012). In particular, the new high-quality, low-cost VA system led to improved clinical performance and quality of care, patient satisfaction, access and operational efficiency, information management, and education and research (Chapko & Van Deusen Lukas; Kenneth W. Kizer & Dudley, 2009; Schall et al., 2004).

Through the implementation of the EHR system, primary care team care models, and quality improvement measures, the VA system out-performed health systems in similar geographic areas (as compared to the VISNs) in overall quality, chronic disease management, and preventive care (Singh & Kalavar, 2004). As shown in Figure 2 (below), the revamped VA system provided better primary and preventive care on measures such as flu shots, cancer screening, and controlling diabetes and blood pressure, as compared to both private insurance and public insurance (Medicare, Medicaid) plans, which report data through HEDIS (Glabman, 2007).

Quality was also found to be of similar quality for acute care in VA vs. non-VA settings. The VA reforms lowered mortality risk, and the VA received higher patient satisfaction scores than private-sector hospitals. Innovations like the barcode matching for medications, the EHR system, and automated prescription filling also improved patient safety and reduced medical errors. As of 2005, the “VA filled 231 million prescriptions with an accuracy rate of 99.993%” (Kenneth W. Kizer & Dudley, 2009). The VA was also successful at expanding access to care and primary care while simultaneously improving quality of care (Armstrong et al., 2005).

FIGURE 2. Quality of care indicators: VHA-HEDIS comparisons. Glabman (2007).

Considerations for Sláintecare

Looking at how the VA was able to reform its previously misaligned health system into a fully integrated, high-quality system, there are numerous lessons learned as Ireland undertakes health care reform.

A. Infrastructure and Workforce

One of the negative effects of the VA's restructuring and reforms was that there were some delays in veterans being able to get appointments, due to increased demand. Similarly, if Ireland expands universal coverage to all residents, it is important to have the infrastructure and capacity in place to meet demand. The Sláintecare Report details adding additional facilities and bolstering the health workforce, and work in these areas must start in the near-term if we are to see substantive results by the time that universal care is rolled out to the public. Furthermore, in a fully integrated health system, Ireland could have clinicians of varying levels (e.g. nurses and physicians) delivering primary and preventive care, lessening the burden on GPs.

B. Moving Away from Hospital-Centric Care

As shown in the VA example, closing acute care beds and moving towards a primary care-focused system can be controversial. There was some outrage from local leaders about closing VA hospitals in their communities, due to the potential economic impact on the region. Although this was done in conjunction with opening community care clinics, the optics of closing down a hospital or parts of a hospital was not politically palatable. It can also draw backlash from specialists/consultants as the health system re-orientes towards a foundation of primary care.

These will be important considerations for Ireland when determining the facility mix in each CHO, and how care will be delivered through this model. While Ireland may not have as many issues with eliminating excess hospital beds (because there is generally a shortage right now), there could be backlash from consultants about the primary care focus of the Sláintecare reforms and from GPs who view the reforms as burdensome for their practices.

C. High Start-Up Costs for EHR and Health IT Investments

While it is difficult to compare the start-up costs for implementing the VA's EHR system, given that the price-points are from over 20 years ago, it is well demonstrated that EHR implementation is an expensive venture. It will likely cost billions to introduce an EHR system in the Irish healthcare system, and this system must be maintained in the years to come. However, the EHR system was fundamental in both the expansion of universal primary care and the introduction of performance measurement/quality improvement methods in the VA system. It is a necessary investment for any high-functioning, modern health system, and it will be a catalyst for all of the other reforms outlined in the Sláintecare plan.

D. Timeline for Reform

The VA reforms occurred under the focused leadership of Kenneth Kizer and took place in under 5 years. In a promising first step to reform, Ireland has set up a Sláintecare Implementation Office under the Ministry of Health. With the timeline for reform currently set at 10-plus years, officials will need to consider what can be accomplished in both the short-term and long-term, knowing that some changes might take longer to roll out, but leadership is needed in the short-term to make sure momentum is not lost.

E. Reducing Waiting Times

With the fallout from the wars in Afghanistan and Iraq, the VA began to serve more veterans than in previous decades, with enrolment increasing from 7.7 million veterans in 2005 to about 9 million in 2014. Despite the historic progress that the VA health system had made in improving care and veterans' health outcomes, this uptick in participation created access issues in some areas of the country. From 2012 to 2014, a series of reports were released highlighting "significant delays in access to care" in the Phoenix, Arizona VA health system, as well as inappropriate scheduling practices nationwide (Chokshi, 2014). In order to alleviate the backlog of veterans waiting for care, Congress passed the Veterans Access, Choice and Accountability Act in 2014. Largely known as the Choice Act, this legislation provided an additional \$10 billion in funding for the VA, as well as creating the Veterans Choice program which allowed veterans to access non-VA care if they were unable to schedule an appointment at a VA facility within 30 days or if they lived more than 40 miles driving distance from the closest VA provider (Vanneman et al., 2017).

While laudable in its goal, there were several issues in implementation of the Choice program that emerged. First, Congress mandated that the Choice program must be in operation within 90 days of the passage of legislation. This left VA providers with little time to prepare for the changes and set up adequate community networks, as well as issues with communication and coordination with the sub-contractors providing care via the Choice program (Mattocks, Mengeling, Sadler, Baldor, & Bastian, 2017). Additionally, experts also highlighted the risk of care fragmentation, as veterans in the Choice program become dual health system users, with their medical information being stored in two different EHR systems and a lack of data-sharing between VA and private providers (Gellad, 2016). Federal watchdog groups (e.g. OIG and GAO) also found that the Choice program contractors left veterans with wait times still longer than what is mandated by law, and at a much higher cost than care within the public VA system (S. Jones, 2018).

If Ireland seeks to alleviate waiting times and improve access to care in an overburdened public system, policymakers should be careful to avoid the mistakes of the VA Choice program. Ireland should choose any private providers and/or contractors carefully and ensure accountability mechanisms, or perhaps dedicate funding to the public system itself in place of outsourcing.

2) Scottish NHS system: Learning by Doing & Integration

The National Health Service (NHS) in Scotland was created in 1948, but has changed most significantly since healthcare was devolved to the Scottish parliament in 1999. While underpinned by the United Kingdom’s NHS system which provides comprehensive, need-based health services funded via general taxation, NHS Scotland has emerged as an exemplar health system in its own right (Robson, 2016). Integration of health and social care has been a priority for NHS Scotland since devolution, and the Scottish have achieved better integration than any other UK country, according to a 2013 study (Ham, Heenan, Longley, & Steel, 2013; Taylor, 2015). NHS Scotland abolished the “purchaser/provider split” inherited from the pre-devolution NHS system, and instead established regional NHS Boards, which are responsible for both planning and delivering care across 14 geographic regions of Scotland (NHS Scotland; The Nuffield Trust, 2011). While Scotland continues to have a higher mortality rate than its British counterparts (McCartney et al., 2015), it has been able to improve health outcomes in targeted areas through specific quality improvement efforts, clinician engagement, and integration of services (Dayan & Edwards, 2017). The Scottish NHS system could be a helpful example for Irish reform due to its similar population size and geographic size, which are roughly equivalent and both grapple with disparities in access to care for rural regions.

FIGURE 3. Scottish Health System Structure. Nuffield Trust (2017).

Parallels in Health System Issues: Scottish NHS and the Irish system

A. Health Workforce Recruitment & Aging Population

NHS Scotland is currently facing a health workforce recruitment challenge, especially for general practitioners (GPs). The aging population means that GPs are retiring, while more GPs are needed to care for Scotland's overall aging population. Bolstering the GP workforce is also well-aligned with Scotland's push to move care out of hospitals and into community care settings, when applicable (Cunningham, Kane, & Denney, 2018). In addition to general practice, Scotland has also seen a rise in vacancy rates for nurses and consultants (especially in psychiatry) (Dayan & Edwards, 2017). Ireland is facing similar difficulties with health workforce recruitment and retention, and also would need more GPs and primary care providers to carry out the Sláintecare reforms.

B. Challenging Financial Environment

Similar to how Ireland has not yet secured the funding necessary to implement universal access to care through the Sláintecare reforms, NHS Scotland is also facing financial challenges. With rising cost pressures, NHS Scotland is finding it difficult to maintain its high standard of care and to keep waiting times low, with the current budget allotment (Christie, 2015). Costs have been increasing with need for services also increasing, putting strain on the health boards of NHS Scotland. A majority of the country's 14 health boards anticipated an unbalanced budget for 2017/18. This has also resulted in Scotland not being able to meet several waiting times targets in recent years, which is a similar trend across the UK. Leaders in the Scottish health system mentioned that the focus on finances and targets of just the current or upcoming year could derail larger system progress, which often requires long-term strategies in order to generate savings and improve health outcomes (Dayan & Edwards, 2017). As Ireland moves to implement universal care, health system leaders should take note of the rising cost challenges present in the Scottish and UK NHS system and potential strategies for mitigation.

Scottish Innovations

A. Integration

While there has been a movement across the entire NHS system to integrate health care services with related services, such as social care, Scotland has been particularly successful. Over the past two decades, the Scottish Parliament and NHS Scotland have pushed for integrated care as a means to improve health in the lowest cost, least-intensive settings necessary. Scotland NHS's move toward integrated, population health with strong linkages to social care and emphasis on community care (rather than hospital-centric care) is well-aligned with the Sláintecare plans for Ireland.

Integrated care was first made a priority with the creation of NHS Scotland's 14 regional health boards, by better aligning incentives for reducing costs and improving health outcomes for a specific geographic population (Taylor, 2015). Throughout the early 2000s, there were a variety of examples of integrated care at the local level or in specific care settings, but Scotland struggled to achieve widespread change. The Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014 was the first major legislation to mandate country-wide integration efforts across Scotland, through the creation of 31 local integration authorities, which would complement the regional health boards. The legislation defined the principles of the integration of health and social care services in Scotland and required health boards and integration authorities to provide integrated care for adults, leaving children's integrated care as an optional add-on for localities. The main goals of the legislation were to improve the quality of care, to provide "joined up" care that allows people to stay in their homes and out of the hospitals as much as possible, and to use resources effectively and efficiently to meet patients' complex needs (Taylor, 2015).

The Scottish integration authorities oversee spending around £8 billion, and are responsible for the integration of emergency hospital care, as well as primary care and outpatient care. The integration legislation was heralded as a success for Scotland because it clearly delegated both mandatory and optional powers for the local integration authorities and also formalized the involvement of local government in integration initiatives. Scottish leaders note that the legislation was more of a "catalyst" than a solution in and of itself, giving localities ownership over the integration work and its performance. Additionally, many Scottish health leaders noted that it can be politically difficult to be seen as advocating for moving care out of the hospital setting, another challenge that Ireland may experience in moving to an integrated health care system (Dayan & Edwards, 2017).

B. Quality Improvement

Scotland's efforts on integrated care go hand-in-hand with quality improvement efforts, which are seen as a hallmark of the NHS Scotland system. Scotland's unique approach to quality improvement involves championing the efforts of frontline staff across all levels of care and providing continuous learning opportunities. When designing performance measurement targets, clinicians are consulted in the process to that success is defined in a way that makes sense for the setting and motivates clinicians to provide excellent care. Scotland also benefits from a "learning by doing" and rapid quality improvement approach, which fits well with its small size as a country (Dayan & Edwards, 2017).

Keys to Scotland's Quality Improvement Success:

1. A sustained commitment to quality improvement over time with a "clear, long-term and uncontested agenda" on quality;
2. The intrinsic, ethical motivations of Scottish clinicians to improve patient outcomes;
3. The lack of strict hierarchy that allows clinicians from all levels to engage in quality improvement efforts;
4. Small-scale, rapid testing of quality improvement initiatives, with a path to implementation and expansion;
5. Scotland's healthcare inspector/regulator and quality improvement bodies are co-located, which leads to improved performance management;
6. Empowering and equipping staff with the skills needed for quality improvement in care delivery and working together to improve outcomes through integrated care (Dayan & Edwards, 2017).

Examples of Scottish Quality Improvement & "Learning by Doing" Efforts:

B1. Scottish Patient Safety Programme

The Scottish Patient Safety Programme (SPSP) was implemented in 2008 with the lofty goal of reducing mortality in Scotland's hospitals by 15 percent in five years (Haraden & Leitch, 2011). The SPSP has since been heralded as the "keystone of quality improvement in Scotland" and been examined by NHS England as an exemplar approach to patient safety (Dayan & Edwards, 2017; Trueland, 2014). NHS Scotland leadership worked with local health boards, Quality Improvement Scotland, and the US-based Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) on SPSP development and implementation. The Scottish and American groups were meant to work collaboratively with one another as "one team" with a shared mission, and local health boards were each asked to designate a patient safety program manager and an executive leader (Haraden & Leitch, 2011).

The programme's key factors for improving patient safety included: local health boards getting clinician buy-in; setting patient safety as a national priority; establishing a learning system to train clinicians on quality improvement and patient safety; and aligning clinical guidelines and definitions of safe, high-quality care across the health system (Haraden & Leitch, 2011). In practice, this meant training clinicians and healthcare administrators, updating clinical practice, testing new modes of care, and monitoring the results (Dayan & Edwards, 2017). Less than three years after implementing the SPSP, hospital mortality rates and hospital-acquired infection rates have both been reduced (Haraden & Leitch, 2011). Given the programme's success, the SPSP model has been expanded to primary care, maternal and child health, medicines, and mental health, and NHS Scotland is also exploring expansion to primary dental care (Healthcare Improvement Scotland iHub; Yeung, 2016).

B2. Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model to rapidly test and scale up innovations

The Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model is a core component of the Scottish Patient Safety Programme, described above. The PDSA model was developed by the US-based Institute for Healthcare Improvement, who adapts quality improvement methodologies to real-world healthcare settings (Walley & Gowland, 2004). Using PDSA cycles allows clinicians and health system leaders to “test out changes on a small scale, building on the learning from these test cycles in a structured way before wholesale implementation,” creating a culture of continuous improvement (NHS Improvement). PDSA has been used in NHS Scotland across a variety of quality improvement initiatives, including improving patient safety in acute care settings and infectious disease preparedness (Curran & Bunyan, 2012). This approach has been shown to be more successful in NHS Scotland than in other contexts, such as NHS England, due to its relatively informal approach for testing out new approaches and scaling them up across facilities. The use of PDSA cycles in NHS Scotland represents a more grassroots, bottom-up approach to quality improvement, rather than a formalized, top-down approach as seen in NHS England and elsewhere (Dayan & Edwards, 2017).

FIGURE 4. PDSA Cycle. NHS Improvement (2018).

B3. Improvement Hub (iHub) Scotland for integration and quality improvement

Created in 2016 under the auspices of Healthcare Improvement Scotland, Improvement Hub (known as “iHub”) promotes continuous improvement in the delivery of health and social care services across Scotland (Healthcare Improvement Scotland iHub). The iHub supports providers across the health, social care, and housing spheres to re-design services for improved integration, quality, and health outcomes. The iHub now houses the Scottish Patient Safety Programme, as well as numerous national efforts on acute care, people-led care, mental health, dementia, community living, health and housing, quality management, primary care, and strategic planning (Healthcare Improvement Scotland iHub). The iHub accomplishes its work by training providers and health system leaders through resources and toolkits; running improvement programmes, learning networks, and trainings; and by granting funds to NHS boards for quality improvement and integration initiatives (Healthcare Improvement Scotland iHub). Examples of resources include the Diabetes Think Check Act toolkit, the Sepsis Toolkit, and Ready to Lead for guiding quality improvement efforts (Healthcare Improvement Scotland iHub). Overall, the iHub plays a valuable role in housing many of Scotland’s quality improvement and integration programmes, helping to better link health and social care for improved health outcomes across Scotland.

C. Health Workforce: Clinician Engagement, Training, and Addressing Disparities

Scotland’s quality improvement and integration success is aided by its unique health workforce culture and use of frontline engagement. NHS Scotland employs about 158,000 staff (which includes nurses, midwives, and some consultants), while over 12,000 physicians, dentists, and other allied health professionals operate as contractors within the NHS system (Haraden & Leitch, 2011). Similarly, Ireland’s public health service employs over 116,000 WTEs (whole time equivalents) through the HSE and Section 38 agencies, and Ireland also has over 20,000 physicians (Irish Department of Health, 2018b; Medical Council of Ireland, 2016). The number of clinicians in NHS Scotland and the Irish system are almost equivalent, but the Scottish system provides universal access to care and has a different working ethos.

C1. “Partnership Working” and Frontline Engagement

Structurally, staff engagement and working across hierarchical structures is embedded in NHS Scotland through the “**Partnership Working**” approach, which governs employee and industrial relations through a transparent, collaborative lens. In this model, the Scottish government, NHS Scotland employers, and NHS Scotland trade unions/professional organizations work in partnership to make decisions and develop policies, with the goal that staff have a say in all changes that affect them. Representatives from these three entities sit on two national bodies: the Scottish Partnership Forum, which works to improve health services in Scotland, and the Scottish Workforce and Staff Governance Committee, which addresses employment policy and workforce issues. Through its strengths of consensus-building, honesty, and openness, the Partnership Working model has been noted as “probably the most ambitious and important contemporary innovation in British public sector industrial relations” in an independent review (NHS Scotland Staff Governance). This way of working ensures that employees and clinicians from all levels of NHS Scotland are involved in the decisions which impact them and can be involved in system-wide improvements.

In addition to this structural element, the culture of NHS Scotland is one that relies less on hierarchy and more on “intrinsic ethical and professional motivations and personal connections between tiers of the hierarchy to bring about change, supported by specific data that focus on patient outcomes” (Dayan & Edwards, 2017). Further, NHS Scotland has emphasized developing a culture of **frontline engagement** where staff have input on clinical decisions and system changes, across all levels of hierarchy. One example is the implementation of “surgical pauses” into the care environment. These short meetings, only five to ten minutes each, bring staff at all levels together at the start of the day to discuss any care and safety concerns. The surgical pauses were an outgrowth of the Scottish Patient Safety Programme at one hospital in Larbert, Scotland, and received support from the Scottish government and senior leaders, who have expanded the practice (Trueland, 2014). Furthermore, NHS Scotland utilizes a coproduction approach when attempting system-wide changes or employee engagement work, knowing that clinicians and staff must have ownership over reforms in order to achieve best outcomes. Through the Staff Experience Continuous Improvement framework (Figure 5, below), NHS Scotland clinicians and staff work in teams to improve care delivery and health outcomes. In evaluating this employee engagement and change framework, the key factors to success included:

- “Change must have a specific purpose;
- All staff need to buy into the idea at all levels of the organisation – systemic;
- Benefits to all have to be clearly explained and highlighted to create involvement, ownership and a sense of empowerment; and
- There have to be clear and defined reciprocal expectations from all those involved (NHS Scotland Staff Governance, 2013)”

FIGURE 5: Staff Experience Continuous Improvement Cycle. NHS Scotland National Staff Experience Final Report and Recommendations (2013).

C2. Scottish Medical Education

As of 2017, there were approximately 5,600 students in medical training in Scotland, across five medical schools. The NHS Education for Scotland (NES) special health board has responsibility for medical training and education at the undergraduate, postgraduate, and continuing education levels, and also oversees the Scottish Deanery which manages postgraduate medical training programmes. In fall 2018, Scotland launched ScotGEM, the first Scottish graduate entry medical education programme. Previously, all medical education was undergraduate entry level only (General Medical Council UK, 2018).

In the UK General Medical Council's (GMC) 2017-2018 review of medical education and training in Scotland, auditors noted the following strengths of the Scottish system:

- **Identifying patient safety concerns:** almost all universities had an online system where medical students could submit safety and quality concerns. By providing medical students the chance to report potential errors or lapses in quality care, this furthers NHS Scotland's culture of identifying safety concerns across all levels of clinicians.
- **Identifying students at different stages of training:** NHS training facilities use colour-coded named badges to identify students and trainees at various levels, so that trainees are not asked to work beyond their competence level. However, the GMC did note the need to standardize the colours used across health boards.
- **Expanding access to medical education:** many of the medical degree programs participated in Reach Scotland, a national programme that provides guidance and resources (e.g. summer school programmes) to students looking to apply to medical school or other high-demand subjects, especially those from underserved or typically underrepresented backgrounds (General Medical Council UK, 2018).

Another noted strength of the Scottish medical education system is problem-based learning (PBL), which “reinforces the study of the fundamentals of medicine in context together with developing clinical reasoning and decision-making” (The University of Edinburgh). Instead of just learning the biological information related to the gastrointestinal system or the neurologic system, PBL allows students to integrate their knowledge across disciplines and apply it to clinically-oriented case studies (University of Glasgow).

C3. Addressing Workforce Shortages: General Practitioners and Rural Care

Not dissimilar to Ireland, Scotland has an ageing population, rural geography, and a shortage of some physician types. Rural and remote regions face difficulty in attracting and retaining physicians of all types, and there is a need for more general practitioners (GPs) country-wide (Richards, Farmer, & Selvaraj, 2005). Below are some of the approaches that NHS Scotland has employed to meet to bolster the health workforce and meet the health needs of all Scottish residents, even in the most remote areas:

- **Consultant Rotation:** Some of the most remote NHS Scotland regions operate consultant rotation programmes to provide specialist care to smaller, rural hospitals. In NHS Highland, clinicians rotate between smaller and larger hospitals in order to provide equitable access to care across facility types. In the city of Aberdeen, clinicians rotate to the northern isles to provide care at smaller, remote facilities. These rotation programmes allow physicians to continue developing their specialist skills, while exposing them to the more generalist needs of smaller hospitals (Dayan & Edwards, 2017).
- **GP Fellowship Programmes:** NHS Scotland is testing a three-year **GP Community Fellowship**, which combines primary and secondary care with mentorship in order to attract more GPs who do not want to be limited to primary care. Initial evaluations of the fellowship showed that there was significant interest in this collaborative training model, which made providers skilled across both inpatient and outpatient settings, but the mentorship/education component would need to be strengthened (Cunningham et al., 2018). Furthermore, the NHS Education for Scotland (NES) board and the rural health boards co-run the **GP Rural Fellowship** programme, where fellows work about half of their year in a rural or remote practice, primarily in the Highland region (NHS Highland).
- **Medical Education for Rural/Remote Care:** Aberdeen School of Medicine offers a “Remote and Rural” specialization option in year four of medical training, where students are placed at NHS Shetland and Western Isles, but use technology-aided education to attend lessons from the mainland. The new graduate entry medical programme, ScotGEM hosted by St. Andrews

and Dundee Schools of Medicine, will incorporate rural/remote care to the Highlands and Western Isles regions (General Medical Council UK, 2018).

- Use of Advanced Nurse Practitioners (ANPs) and Telemedicine: Many rural and remote regions in Scotland (e.g. Highlands, Western Isles, Shetland, Orkney) utilize ANPs to provide primary care to residents, with the oversight of a visiting GP. The ANPs have prescribing power and also triage patients, referring to GP or consultant care when needed. These regions also use video or phone connections to physicians on the mainland (or in more populated areas) for consultation on outpatient procedures or follow-up care. Telemedicine's use has included orthopaedic surgery follow-up in Shetland and nurse-led chemotherapy and dialysis in Orkney (Dayan & Edwards, 2017).

Reform Outcomes

Given the recent timeframe for implementation and the many reform components since healthcare was devolved to Scotland in 1999, it is difficult to evaluate the exact outcomes for Scottish health. However, there are a few key findings that highlight the potential utility of the NHS Scotland model. First, the Scottish Patient Safety Programme (SPSP) resulted in 12.4% lower hospital mortality rates over the first five years over the program, which amounts to 10,500 fewer deaths (Trueland, 2014). Hospital-acquired infection rates have also decreased, and the SPSP model is so promising that it has been expanded to other healthcare settings (e.g. primary care) and is also being implemented in NHS England (Haraden & Leitch, 2011). Looking at integration, Scotland's Public Bodies (Joint Working) Act of 2014 represented "one of the single biggest changes to care services in Scotland," but is it still too soon for any tangible results (Bruce & Parry, 2015).

Considerations for Sláintecare

A. Financial Sustainability and Waiting Times

An Audit Scotland report released this fall shows that NHS Scotland is facing financial sustainability issues, with many of the health boards struggling to break even and meet key waiting time targets. This concern was noted as early as 2015, with many health boards needing additional government funding to provide high-quality, timely services (Christie, 2015). In response, the Scottish government plans to invest £850m over the next three years to ensure that NHS Scotland can meet waiting time targets and continue to provide high-quality care (BBC, 2018). Similarly, Ireland will need to ensure proper financial resources before entitling residents to universal healthcare, especially since need will only increase as the population ages.

B. Health Workforce

Scotland is testing out many innovative models to recruit and retain physicians in general practice, as well as in rural and remote regions. Ireland has both the need for rural care, as well as shortages in the medical workforce. In particular, Ireland is having difficulty retaining recent medical graduates, who are often leaving Ireland in search of employment in other English-speaking nations. In a recent survey by the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, poor working conditions and a lack of training and career advancement opportunities were noted as the key causes for medical trainee emigration (RCSI Health Workforce Research Group, 2018). For Ireland to enact the sweeping Sláintecare reforms, serious change will be needed in the health workforce, to ensure adequate numbers of providers, as well as a workforce that is both highly skilled and highly motivated. This could be a potential opportunity to bring in the "partnership working" model, where HSE staff, clinicians, and health system leaders could work collaboratively implement to Sláintecare. Giving each clinician and staff member in the Irish system the chance to weigh in on changes, and feel represented in the reform process, will be crucial for securing buy-in and achieving system-wide change.

C. Integration

Scotland's Health Boards and Integration Authorities serve as the principal mechanism of delivering integrated care at the regional level. Given Ireland's similar geographic and population size, these boards could serve as a model for care organization here in Ireland. In particular, the Irish CHOs could be tasked with both regionally planning and delivering care, but also with integrating health and social care services. While an ambitious goal, integration is in the Sláintecare vision and represents the future of service delivery for a more community-based healthcare system.

D. Long-term Vision

With the publication and adoption of the Sláintecare Report, Ireland has achieved cross-party consensus on a vision for the future of Irish healthcare. This consistency is crucial for creating a high-quality and high-performing system. Having a “clear, long-term and uncontested agenda” has been noted as a key feature of the Scottish NHS system’s success (Dayan & Edwards, 2017). The literature also supports that a sustained focus and long timespan is needed for system-level change and quality improvement. Ireland’s leaders – in the Oireachtas, the Ministry of Health, and the HSE – must keep the momentum going and ensure a long-term commitment to the implementation of Sláintecare. While there might be divergence of opinion in how to structure and finance the Sláintecare reforms, keeping leaders aligned with the vision will be crucial to Irish healthcare reform.

3) New Zealand system: Local Governance and Structure

Since the passage of the 1938 Social Security Act, there has been consensus in New Zealand that the government should have some involvement in providing healthcare for its citizens. The New Zealand health system has been gradually reformed over time, but the 2000-2002 reforms from the Labour-Alliance coalition government have been most impactful on the current system (New Zealand Parliament, 2009). Today, New Zealand has a universal healthcare system funded via general tax revenues, where geographically-defined District Health Boards (DHBs) are responsible for planning and providing care. Public healthcare spending is about 80 percent, while there is still 20 percent in private spending, including co-payments and private insurance (Robin Gauld, 2016). The New Zealand health system is often noted as one of the best in the world. In a 2017 study from The Commonwealth Fund comparing the health systems of eleven high-income nations, New Zealand ranked fourth overall, scoring particularly well in the care process and administrative efficiency categories (Schneider, Sarnak, Squires, Shah, & Doty, 2017). New Zealand also provides a relevant case study for Irish health reform due to its roughly equivalent population size (NZ: 4.8 million; Republic of Ireland: 4.7 million).

FIGURE 6. General New Zealand healthcare structure. Chin (2018).

Parallels in Health System Issues: New Zealand and the Irish system

A. Barriers to Primary Care

While New Zealand has a universal healthcare system, only public hospital services are truly “free.” For most patients, co-payments are required for general practitioner (GP) services, as well as most nursing services provided in the primary care setting. The average co-payment for an adult visiting a GP is around NZD15 to NZD45, which equates to about €9 to €27 euros per consultation, depending on the fee set by the individual GP (Robin Gauld, 2016). While this is still cheaper than in Ireland, where a GP visit averages €40 to €60 euros, it still creates a barrier to access and can undermine the goals of a preventative, integrated health system (O’Regan, 2015). A 2009 study found that about 15.5 percent of New Zealanders had deferred seeing their primary care physician in the past year due to cost (Jatrana & Crampton, 2009). However, New

Zealand has tried to address this by capping patient co-payments in lower-income areas (Chin et al., 2018). Similar to Ireland, New Zealand does have a scheme for free GP visits for children, with all children under age 13 receiving primary care at no charge (Robin Gauld, 2016).

Furthermore, there is not universal coverage for dental services in New Zealand, with only children and adolescents provided dental care through school-based schemes. Most adults are responsible for financing their own dental care, which is an often-neglected part of primary care, and the same study found that almost 23 percent of New Zealanders put off seeing a dentist in the last year due to cost barriers (Jatrana & Crampton, 2009). Similarly, Ireland will need to explore financing options for expanding primary care access, including dental care, through the Sláintecare reforms.

B. Mixed Public-Private System

While New Zealand has a universal, public healthcare system it is similar to Ireland in that it is also a two-tiered system, where those with private insurance can gain quicker access to diagnostic services, specialist care, and elective procedures. About one-third of New Zealanders have private health insurance, while lower-income individuals rely solely on the public system for their care needs and may have longer wait times for care (Chin et al., 2018).

Additionally, hospitals are generally public entities, where specialists are employed and salaried by the district health boards (DHBs) to provide public care. However, specialists (i.e. consultants) can also work as private providers in their own clinics or at private hospitals, where patients with private health insurance or those who can afford hefty out-of-pocket costs can receive expedited care. The Commonwealth Fund notes that this “dual practice” and its impact on the public sector is largely under-researched. Conversely, primary care is provided through private physicians who contract with the DHBs to provide services (Robin Gauld, 2016). This was the result of the bargaining power of GPs to influence New Zealand’s health reform trajectory, discussed in more detail in the following sections. Overall, only 60 percent of primary healthcare is government-funded, with the rest falling to individuals (via co-payments, private insurance, etc.) (Jatrana & Crampton, 2009).

NZ Innovations

A. Local Governance of Healthcare Services

New Zealand has a history of local governance in healthcare dating back to the establishment of Area Health Boards (AHBs) in 1983. During 1993 to 1997, New Zealand abolished the AHBs in favour of state-run, for-profit Crown Health Enterprises. However, this approach was thought to be lacking in consumer input, accountability, and health promotion. In 2000, the Labour-Alliance Coalition Government implemented major health reform through the New Zealand Public Health and Disability Act. This legislation created numerous changes in the structure of New Zealand’s health system, namely the creation of 21 District Health Boards (DHBs; now 20) and a revamped Ministry of Health. In 2002, this government also introduced Primary Health Organizations (PHOs) to organize general practitioner (GP) services as part of the country’s Primary Health Care Strategy. Changes resulting from the New Zealand Public Health and Disability Act 2000 and the Primary Health Care Strategy form the basis of New Zealand’s health system today, which provides for local governance of health planning and care delivery, while still granting autonomy to physicians (New Zealand Parliament, 2009). This is, perhaps, a helpful model for Irish health reform, as Ireland looks to restructure care planning and delivery by CHOs, which would operate at a regional level.

FIGURE 7. New Zealand's health system structure, 2008. Parliament of New Zealand (2009).

A1. District Health Boards

One of the biggest reforms from the New Zealand Public Health and Disability Act 2000, which continues to shape the health system today, was the introduction of District Health Boards (DHBs), which provide care for geographic regions of New Zealand. The legislation delegated authority for health planning, funding, and provision to the regional DHBs, abolishing the centralized “Health Funding Authority” which had central purchasing power. Through the establishment of DHBs, New Zealand’s leaders sought to re-focus the health system on health outcomes, democratize health service delivery, and end the purchaser-provider split which previously characterized New Zealand’s health system. The DHBs are tasked with not only running public hospitals, but also providing health services, including primary and community care, and meeting the public health needs of their district (Starke, 2010).

The 20 DHBs are “Crown entities that are responsible to the Minister of Health and funded via a population-based formula” and are governed by an 11-member board. On each DHB board, seven members are elected from the local community, while four are appointed by the Ministry of Health (New Zealand Parliament, 2009). While DHBs operate somewhat autonomously, the Ministry of Health sets national policy targets and long-term strategies for health improvement, which DHBs must integrate into their regional work (Starke, 2010). In recognition of health equity, the population-based funding formula, which determines funding to each DHB, is now adjusted by the New Zealand Index of Deprivation, so that areas with more inequalities receive greater funding for health services (Chin et al., 2018).

FIGURE 8. District Health Boards map. New Zealand Ministry of Health (2017).

A2. Primary Health Organisations

With the growing recognition of the importance of primary care and population health management, such as through the WHO Declaration of Alma-Ata, ensuring that New Zealanders had access to primary and preventive care was also essential in the early 2000s healthcare reforms (R. Gauld, 2012). In 2001, the New Zealand government released the nation's Primary Health Care Strategy, which aimed to organize general practitioners (GPs) into Primary Health Organisations (PHOs). Formally established in 2002, these non-profit, community-based groups consist of not only physicians, but also nurses, pharmacists, psychologists, physiotherapists, and other types of community and allied health workers (New Zealand Parliament, 2009). This was an outgrowth of previous reform efforts, the influence of GPs on health reform, and a movement towards managed care which was occurring in many developed nations (e.g. USA) (Starke, 2010).

Primary Health Organisations contract with the DHBs to provide primary care services for a set geographic population. As of 2008, there were 80 PHOs providing care to over 4 million New Zealanders – about 95 percent of the population (Starke, 2010). The PHOs are funded on a capitation basis to care for their enrollees, regardless of whether contact is made in a given year. The GPs are paid primarily by their PHO, but then can set their own co-payment fee. Primary care visit co-payments could vary widely and there were many concerns about access to primary care for underserved populations. To address this, New Zealand subsidizes PHOs operating in deprived areas, so co-payment rates have fallen and access has improved. However, there is still no universal, free access to primary care, except for specific populations (i.e. children under 13) (Jatrana & Crampton, 2009).

A3. Post-2008 Reforms for Integration: District Alliances

With 20 District Health Boards and 80 Primary Health Organisations, there were fair concerns about care coordination and integration across the New Zealand health system. Achieving integrated care, particularly between primary care (via PHOs) and secondary/hospital care (via DHBs), has become a priority for New Zealand in the last decade. In 2009, the New Zealand government announced its intention to create a more patient-centred, integrated health system where care is delivered “closer to home,” which is also in keeping with the Irish Sláintecare vision (Cumming, 2011). To achieve this, New Zealand started to create district alliances (DAs) to foster improved integration across the health system (Chalmers, Ashton, & Tenbensen, 2017).

In 2009, nine alliances were selected to deliver new models of integrated and coordinated care across New Zealand. An alliance involves the DHBs, PHOs, and other provider types working collaboratively to improve health across a geographic region under one governance structure. In addition to providing more coordinated care, the alliances have also developed interdisciplinary family health centres to provide integrated care at the community level and are promoting more nurse-led and team-based care (Cumming, 2011). The alliancing structure is somewhat similar to Scotland's addition of local integration authorities, working alongside their NHS local health trusts. Dr Robin Gauld, New Zealand health policy expert, points out that New Zealand's alliancing structure “requires that all providers in a region work collaboratively within a whole system approach to ensure that services are designed with what is best for patients and the public in mind” (Robin Gauld, 2014).

Along with creating alliancing structures, New Zealand sought to decrease the number of PHOs in order to reduce primary care service costs and duplication (Cumming, 2011). As of December 2018, there are now only 31 PHOs, down from 80, but this is still a somewhat shockingly high number given New Zealand's small size (New Zealand Ministry of Health).

B. The Canterbury Model – Lessons Learned & Expansion

The second-largest of New Zealand's 20 District Health Boards (DHBs), the Canterbury DHB went from experiencing some of the largest clinical and financial challenges in the nation, to serving as a model of healthcare transformation on a global scale. In 2006-2007, the Canterbury DHB had a huge financial deficit, as well as the longest waiting times in New Zealand for elective procedures and cancer care. Hospital care measures also showed lagging performance, and it was estimated that Canterbury would require an additional 450 inpatient beds and 8,000 healthcare workers by 2020 if the status quo remained (Gullery & Hamilton, 2015).

Noting these key issues in the Canterbury health system, DHB leaders took on a health services planning process in 2007 in the pursuit of revamping the system to deliver integrated care, with a focus on care at the community level. Originally, 80 senior staff in Canterbury were recruited for the planning exercise, but the DHB then expanded the scope to engage over 2,000 clinicians, staff, and consumers in order to shape the vision and expand participation in the transformation process. With the feedback and

input of these individuals, the Canterbury DHB began implementing changes in 2008 to re-orient the system towards primary and community-based care, and improve the overall patient experience. Through a myriad of changes, Canterbury has lowered its inpatient admittance rates, average length of stay, readmission rates, and waiting times for elective surgery. General Practitioners are now treating many health conditions in the primary care setting, rather than the hospital setting, saving both time and money. As part of the reforms, GPs also have increased access to diagnostic testing, which has shortened the wait time for them and made for easier referral to specialist care (Timmins & Ham, 2013).

In a 2017 report looking at lessons learned from Canterbury's reform, the King's Fund noted the development of a clear, unified vision through clinician and staff engagement as one of the three essential elements of the Canterbury model's success. The overarching concept of "one system, one budget" emerged and was used as a guiding principle for the changes across Canterbury. Second, the King's fund identified investing in staff as a key element of success. Similar to the Scottish model, Canterbury staff and clinicians have been empowered to lead implementation of the reforms and change management efforts. Lastly, developing new forms of contracting was identified as the third essential key to Canterbury's success. The alliancing model discussed in the preceding section ("Post-2008 Reforms for Integration: District Alliances") allows organizations to work together to improve health outcomes, while also remaining financially sustainable. Canterbury DHB provides block grants to providers, rather than paying for the level of hospital activity, which re-aligns incentives to improve overall health outcomes and reduce the level of hospital admissions (A. Charles, 2017). The alliancing model has spread across New Zealand, albeit being only one piece of Canterbury's overall system reform (Toop, 2017).

Noted by the King's Fund as one of the most impactful innovations from Canterbury's system transformation, HealthPathways was developed in Canterbury in 2008 (A. Charles, 2017). HealthPathways is an online manual for clinicians that provides them with assistance for assessing and treating health conditions, as well as referring out for local services (McGonigle & McGeoch, 2017). In Canterbury, the HealthPathways system has resulted in a 43 percent increase in access to elective surgery and a dramatic decrease in wait times (Gullery & Hamilton, 2015). The tool can be tailored for the local context, and use of HealthPathways has spread to over 40 organizations across New Zealand, Australia, and the UK (HealthPathways Community, 2019). However, when looking at the expansion of HealthPathways outside of Canterbury, a process evaluation showed difficulties in its implementation for the Southern Health Region of New Zealand (Otago and Southland), finding that the implementation climate and readiness for change were not adequate for the successful adoption of HealthPathways (Stokes, Tumilty, Doolan-Noble, & Gauld, 2018). However, with proper care given to implementation, HealthPathways could be a useful tool in Ireland for developing local pathways to community care and decreasing wait times.

Since the 2013 report from the UK-based King's Fund highlighted the success of the Canterbury model, the approach has spread across New Zealand, and to other countries as well. The Canterbury model proved to be exceptional in its ability to reduce waiting times for care, reduce unnecessary hospitalizations, and re-orient the health system to provide more preventive and primary care (Gullery & Hamilton, 2015). In particular, the alliancing model and the use of the HealthPathways tool have spread across New Zealand. While promising in its initial results, this new integrated family health and community-based care model has yet to be tested and evaluated at scale in other localities (Toop, 2017).

Reform Outcomes

While New Zealand's health system is consistently ranked as one of the best, there is a dearth of evidence about the effects of New Zealand's recent healthcare reforms on access, service delivery, outcomes, and cost. In a 2011 article, New Zealand researcher Dr Jacqueline Cumming notes that "A feature of recent reforms has been the failure to document, evaluate and share innovations and lessons learned in trying to effect change in service delivery." However, a few things have stood out. First, a 2010 international study found that a higher proportion of New Zealanders reported care coordination by their regular doctor (69 percent) than other peer nations, showing that New Zealand's health system may be leading to improved integration and care coordination (Cumming, 2011). This is in line with the 2017 Commonwealth Fund study, where New Zealand's health system ranked fourth overall (out of eleven high-income nations), scoring particularly well in the care process and administrative efficiency categories (Schneider et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the move to all capitated funding for primary care starting in the 2000s, has likely also helped New Zealand to create a more integrated, value-driven health system by opening the door for other provider types to provide primary care services, not just GPs. Lastly, despite the lack of published evaluations on New Zealand's health reforms, the suite of changes (including enhanced primary care access via PHOs, local governance of DHBs, and alliancing for regional-level collaboration) are likely "building blocks" for creating a more integrated, modern health system where care is delivered when and where patients need it, while reducing reliance on traditional hospital-centric models (Cumming, 2011).

Considerations for Sláintecare

A. Waiting Times for Specialist Care

It has been widely reported that New Zealand continues to suffer from access issues for specialty, elective, and emergency care in public hospitals, with long waiting times for certain procedures or provider types (e.g. dermatology, gynaecology, ophthalmology). Similar to Ireland, patients with private insurance can pay to obtain services from a private provider (who may be paid by both public and private funds for delivering services to both patient types) much more quickly than public patients. This is a major equity concern, if it results in higher-income residents receiving timelier care than lower-income patients, which could worsen health disparities. In New Zealand, many public patients have had their referrals to specialists declined due to a lack of resources. Ireland must ensure that the proper workforce, infrastructure, and financing is in place so that Irish patients can be successfully referred to treatment and receive timely care. In New Zealand, there have been overcrowded emergency departments (EDs), so officials have created a program that provides vouchers for care at nearby private clinics, instead of the public ED. Residents have a choice between using or declining the voucher, in which case they would wait for care in the ED where they first presented (N. Jones & Akoorie, 2018). This program is similar to the United States' VA Choice program, which also provides waivers for private care, but evidence is mixed. Ireland should make sure to explore other options (e.g. injections of public funding) and research on these waiver programs before implementing similar initiatives.

B. Barriers to Integrated Care and Network Complexity

New Zealand's health system, while high-functioning in many ways, perpetuates some barriers in access to primary care and limits the adoption of a fully integrated health care system. First, user fees for GP and primary care services limits access to care and can push individuals to put off preventive care and instead utilize emergency or hospital services, when the health issue becomes critical (Cumming, 2011). This is similar to Ireland's current system, where payments for GP visits can also impede individuals from receiving timely preventive care. In the Sláintecare vision, primary care services would be free in Ireland, in the hopes of pursuing a more preventive and community-based health system.

Furthermore, the New Zealand structure of co-existing District Health Boards (DHBs) and Primary Health Organisations (PHOs) siloes primary care, although the post-2008 alliancing reforms seek to integrate the two entities. However, 20 DHBs and 31 PHOs is still a large number for such a small country (similar in size and population to Ireland), so some have recommended further consolidating the number of DHBs and PHOs (Downs, 2017). Similarly, Ireland has nine Community Healthcare Organisations (CHOs) that operate distinctly from the seven Hospital Groups, with CHOs responsible for community health services and Hospital Groups provisioning hospital-based services, as the names imply. The Sláintecare report recommends that Ireland geographically align the CHOs and Hospital Groups, so that there is better integration between community and hospital care across the health system. A 2014 report recommended the creation of 90 primary care networks (approximately 10 for each CHO), but Ireland should be wary of the network complexity that may result (Irish Department of Health, 2018a). For example, New Zealand has reduced the number of PHOs from 80 to now just 31, citing the need to reduce costs and duplication of efforts. Overall, Ireland's health reform efforts should ensure that both the structure and financing of the system leads to the intended goal of introducing: "integrated primary and community care, consistent with the highest quality of patient safety in as short a time-frame as possible" (Committee on the Future of Healthcare, 2017).

4) Evaluation Approaches for Integration

The integration of health and social services is a common theme throughout many health reforms occurring globally today, especially as health budgets are strained and with a growing, aging population. The Sláintecare report highlights the Irish system moving "towards a new model of integrated care...[where] coordinated health and social care is needed to meet the needs of our older population, with its more complex set of clinical and social care needs, and to address the growing prevalence of chronic disease" (Committee on the Future of Healthcare, 2017, p. 20). Researchers and healthcare professionals have made the case that it pays to invest in the bundling of health and social care, with the aim of addressing the social determinants of health and also preventing unnecessary hospitalizations and expensive inpatient care. If a person can have their chronic conditions managed by their GP, receive in-home health services when needed, and be connected with community resources, it could both save the health system money and improve health outcomes (Mason, Goddard, Weatherly, & Chalkley, 2015).

Despite the popularity of integration in many health reform movements today and an extensive literature describing the concept, there is still a surprising lack of evidence on its effects. Evaluating the integration of health and social services can be rather difficult, as it can be challenging to isolate impacts related to integration and there is usually a long time span needed to judge the effects of integration (Goddard & Mason, 2016). And, many evaluations focus on process, rather than outcomes. While it may be difficult to evaluate the outcomes of integrated care, it is essential in order to build the evidence base and guide healthcare reform specific to a particular context. What works for integrating care in the UK or the US may not be effective for Ireland (Exworthy, Powell, & Glasby, 2017).

Nuffield Trust: Evaluating integrated and community-based care guide

Nongovernmental organizations are increasingly publishing guides for policymakers and health researchers to use in their pursuit of evaluating integrated care initiatives. One exemplary resource “Evaluating integrated and community-based care” from the Nuffield Trust outlines key findings from the evaluation of over 30 such programs in the UK, and dedicates an entire section to lessons learned for those leading future implementation and evaluation efforts. The Nuffield Trust guide highlights the need for implementation of integration reforms to be highly linked with monitoring and evaluation. Most evaluations assume that the intervention was implemented perfectly, but this is particularly tricky for health system changes spanning sectors, such as with integration work. Some key points from the Nuffield Trust resource include (Bardsley, Steventon, Smith, & Dixon, 2013):

- Using linked data sets, including data from GPs and primary care settings, to conduct evaluations of integrated care by tracking individuals and their associated health status, quality of care, and health/social care usage.
- Recognizing that implementing wide-scale health system changes, including integration work, takes time and results may not be visible in the short-term. Process evaluation may be possible in the first year or two, but usage and outcome results may not be significant until after a number of years.
- Given the long timespan for implementation and evaluation, set interim markers of success and be specific about how long-term outcomes will be achieved.
- Evaluators often focus in on emergency admissions and hospital usage and costs when looking at the outcomes from integration initiatives. It may take years to realize changes in hospital-based outcomes, so researchers should also utilize clinical health indicators, patient’s self-reported health status, and other variables to look at the changing care experience.
- The use of pilot testing and evaluation of the pilot sites can be critical for examining not only when an intervention should be replicated, but also how evaluation methods should adapt to better measure the impacts of integration (Bardsley et al., 2013).

Lessons Learned for Ireland:

- Monitoring and evaluation need to be built into the Sláintecare reforms in order to have a reliable way of measuring progress and planning for the future.
- Link monitoring and evaluation work to organizational development efforts (e.g. patient safety, quality of care improvement) at clinical sites so that staff and clinicians can be part of the implementation.
- Regularly interview and obtain feedback from local reform leaders and clinicians in order to inform the improvement of integration and health system changes on a national scale, scaling up what works.
- Create feedback loops and use process evaluation to learn what’s working well (and what’s not working) in the implementation of integration work, in order to inform decision-making and make changes in real-time (Bardsley et al., 2013).

Challenges:

Ireland's current data systems may not be sufficient to capture the level of information needed for evaluating the integration of health and social care. It may take investing in a nationwide EHR system and/or the development of nationwide reporting to capture population-level data on integration. For example, currently the HIPE dataset only looks at inpatient data at public hospitals, and therefore does not include emergency department, outpatient, or private hospital data. At minimum, Ireland would need to create a linked dataset that provides patient-level data at the primary, community, and tertiary care levels. Only when we can look at what types of services patients are receiving across all settings of health and social care will we be able to evaluate the effects of integration and the Sláintecare reforms.

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